

Heat and mass transfer characteristics of radiative hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching sheet with chemical reaction

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Abstract:

This study investigates the unsteady magneto-hydrodynamic heat and mass transfer in a hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching surface, considering chemical reactions, suction, slip effects, and thermal radiation. The hybrid nanoparticles used are Alumina (Al₂O₃) and Titanium Oxide (TiO₂), with water serving as the base fluid. By employing the similarity transformation method, the governing equations are converted into a system of ordinary differential equations. These equations, along with the boundary conditions, are numerically solved using the Finite Element Method. The study examines the impact of various parameters on the fluid concentration, temperature, and velocity profiles, presenting the findings through graphical representations. Additionally, the non-dimensional rates of heat transfer, mass transfer, and velocity are analyzed, with the results summarized in tables. It is observed that the temperature profiles of the hybrid nanofluid increase in both steady and unsteady states as the volume fraction of the nanoparticles rises.

Keywords: TiO₂/Al₂O₃ – Water hybrid nanofluid; Magneto-hydrodynamics; chemical reaction; slip effects; thermal radiation; FEM.

1. Introduction

In recent times, the study of nanoliquids has expanded significantly due to their wide range of applications in fields such as biomedicine, heat exchangers, cooling of electronic devices, double glazing, food processing, and transportation. Enhancing the thermal conductivity of base fluids like ethylene glycol, water, kerosene, and engine oils involves adding various nanoparticles, such as graphene, silica, silver, gold, copper, alumina, and carbon nanotubes. Numerous research articles have explored the improvement of base fluid thermal conductivity through the incorporation of these nanoparticles [1 – 6]. Sheremet et al. [7] analyzed heat transfer in a single-phase model of nanoliquid flow within a square inclined cavity filled with water-alumina nanoliquid, where the left wall was maintained at a sinusoidal temperature. Bondarenko et al. [8] investigated the cooling of a heat-generating and heat-conducting element within an enclosure filled with water-Al₂O₃ nanoliquid with a moving top wall, finding that the heated element cooled rapidly at high Reynolds numbers. Dogonchi et al. [9] observed an increase in the heat transfer coefficient with higher volume fractions of nanoparticles in their study of heat transfer through a cold external circular cylinder and a hot internal rectangular cylinder filled with water-Cu nanoliquid. Bondarenko et al. [10] examined the effect of cold vertical walls on the cooling of a heat-generating and heat-conducting source within an enclosure filled with water-Al₂O₃ nanoliquid, noting an intensification of the cooling process with higher nanoparticle volume fractions. Mahian et al. [11] reviewed heat transfer analyses of single-phase, multi-phase, and 3D simulations of nanoliquid flows over various geometries. Mikhailenko et al. [12] studied liquid and heat transport in water-Al₂O₃ nanoliquid over rotating cavities, observing a decrease in heat transfer rates with increasing nanoparticle volume fractions. Hashimet al. [13] applied the Finite Element Analysis method to determine the numerical

solutions for nanoliquid heat and flow characteristics in a wavy cavity filled with Al_2O_3 nanoparticles.

"Hybrid nanoliquids" are advanced fluids with superior thermal conductivity compared to standard nanoliquids and base fluids. They share similar applications with nanoliquids, including biomedicine, heat exchangers, electronic device cooling, double glazing, food processing, and transportation, but exhibit enhanced thermal efficiency. Hybrid nanoliquids are created by dispersing two different types of nanoparticles in a base fluid. Ahmadi et al. [14] studied the flow and heat transfer characteristics of Bungiorno's model nanofluid over a heated stretching sheet, noting an increase in the Nusselt number with higher values of the Brownian motion parameter. Qasim et al. [15] analyzed heat and mass transfer in Bungiorno's model nanofluid thin film flow over a stretching sheet, observing a decrease in heat transfer rates with increased Brownian motion parameter values. Biglarian et al. [16] examined the effect of different nanoparticles and their volume fractions on heat transport and flow of unsteady nanofluids between parallel plates. Mahdy et al. [17] found that the skin friction coefficient increased with higher Weissenberg numbers in their study of time-dependent hyperbolic tangential nanofluid flow over a stretching wedge. Hashim et al. [18] explored the impact of thermophoresis and Brownian motion on the mass and heat transfer characteristics of Williamson nanofluid flow over a wedge. Ashtania et al. [19] conducted an unsteady natural convection flow analysis of nanofluid within a partially porous cavity using a thermal non-equilibrium model with a local heat-generating solid element. Yarmand et al. [20] demonstrated enhanced heat transfer in a hybrid nanofluid composed of platinum/graphene nanoplatelets in water within a four-sided microchannel with constant heat flux boundaries. Studies [21, 22] numerically investigated the heat transfer capabilities of Al_2O_3 -Cu/water hybrid nanofluid. Sundar et al. [23] reviewed the heat transfer

properties of various hybrid nanofluids, highlighting their superior performance. Ghalambaz et al. [24] conducted pioneering research on the melting process of nanoparticle-enhanced phase-change materials in hybrid nanofluid flow over a square cavity using the Finite Element Method, which was further investigated in [25]. Wei et al. [26] observed a maximum 8.39% increase in the thermal conductivity of diathermic oil-SiC/TiO₂ based hybrid nanofluid at a 1% nanoparticle volume fraction. Huminić et al. [27] analyzed the heat transfer characteristics of two hybrid nanofluids, Fe₃O₄/MWCNT-water and ND/Fe₃O₄-water, over a tube, finding greater thermal conductivity enhancement in the former. Ghalambaz et al. [28] studied the flow characteristics of a hybrid nanofluid within a square porous cavity containing MgO and Ag nanoparticles, noting a decline in the Nusselt number with higher nanoparticle volume fractions. Asadi et al. [29] explored the heat transfer efficiency of MWCNT/Al₂O₃-thermal oil hybrid nanofluid as a cooling fluid in energy management. Kumar et al. [30] conducted both theoretical and experimental investigations into heat transfer enhancement in MWCNT/Al₂O₃-water nanofluid flow over a minichannel heat sink, noting a 30-35% increase in heat transfer coefficient as the hydraulic diameter decreased. Khodadadi et al. [31] reviewed the rheological properties of hybrid and mono nanofluids, observing an increase in fluid viscosity with higher nanoparticle volume fractions. Sundar et al. [32] experimentally analyzed the heat transfer behavior of ND/Ni-water hybrid nanofluid flow through a tube, achieving a 35.43% increase in heat transfer rates at a 0.3% nanoparticle volume and Reynolds number of 22,000. Hussien et al. [33] experimentally examined the heat transfer characteristics of GNPs/MWCNTs-water hybrid nanofluid flow through a mini tube, finding a 43.4% enhancement in heat transfer rates. Sheikholeslami et al. [34] numerically analyzed the flow characteristics of MHD hybrid nanofluid made from Fe₃O₄ and MWCNT in water within an enclosure with double heaters,

noting an increase in heat transfer rates. The heat transfer enhancement of Fe₃O₄/MWCNT-water hybrid nanoliquid in a T-shaped cavity with two porous layers was studied using the finite element technique [35, 36]. Chamkha et al. [37] used the finite element method to calculate heat transfer rates of a hybrid nanoliquid comprising copper and alumina nanoparticles in water. Recent studies [38-41] have discussed heat and flow analysis of nanofluids over various geometries filled with suspensions of nano-encapsulated phase change materials.

Careful observation on available literature reveals that no studies have reported to analyze the impact of slip effects and chemical reaction on mass and heat transport characteristics of magneto-hydrodynamic hybridnanoliquids prepared by considering TiO₂/Al₂O₃ as nanoparticles and water as base fluid over stretching sheet. The resultant equations are solved using Finite element method with Mathematica 10.0. The problem addressed in this analysis has immediate applications in generator cooling, transformer cooling, electronic cooling etc.

2. Mathematical Analysis of the problem

Consider unsteady, laminar, two dimensional, MHD boundary layer heat and mass transfer of TiO₂/Al₂O₃ – Water based hybridnanoliquid flow through a stretching sheet with slip effects as depicted in Fig. 1. Along the stretching surface and in the direction of flow the x – axis considered and y – axis is measured normal to it. $U_w(x, t)$ is the velocity of the stretching sheet. A constant magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied normal to the plate. T_w and C_w are considered as sheet surface uniform temperature and concentration, furthermore, T_∞ and C_∞ are taken as ambient fluid temperature and concentration, correspondingly. The thermo-physical properties of the nanoliquid are given in Table 1. Under the above assumptions, the governing equations describing the momentum, energy and concentration in the presence of chemical reaction, slip effects and thermal radiation are given by [Asadi et al. 29].

Fig. 1 . Physical model and Coordinate system.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho_{hnf}} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \nu_{hnf} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\sigma B^2(t)}{\rho_{hnf}} u \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{k_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D_B \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} \quad (4)$$

The following physical boundary conditions are

$$u = U_w + L \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}, \quad v = v_w, \quad T = T_w + k_1 \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}, \quad C = C_w + k_2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial y}, \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_\infty, \quad C \rightarrow C_\infty \quad \text{at } y \rightarrow \infty \quad (6)$$

The subsequent similarity transformations are presented to streamline the mathematical study of the problem

$$\eta = y \sqrt{\frac{a}{\nu_f(1-ct)}}, \quad \psi = x \sqrt{\frac{a\nu_f}{1-ct}} f(\eta), \quad \theta(\eta) = \frac{T-T_\infty}{T_w-T_\infty}, \quad S(\eta) = \frac{C-C_\infty}{C_w-C_\infty} \quad (7)$$

Additionally,

$$U_w(x, t) = \frac{b x}{1-ct}, \quad T_w(x, t) = T_\infty + \frac{T_0 U_w x}{\nu (1-ct)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad C_w(x, t) = C_\infty + \frac{C_0 U_w x}{\nu (1-ct)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad B(t) = \frac{B_0}{(1-ct)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (8)$$

The transformed equations are

$$f''' + \frac{A_2}{A_1} f f'' - \frac{A_2}{A_1} (f')^2 - \frac{A_2}{A_1} \gamma \left\{ f' + \frac{\eta}{2} f'' \right\} - A_1 M f' = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$(1 + A_4 R) \theta'' - Pr \frac{A_3 \gamma}{A_4} (\eta \theta' + 2 \theta') = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$S'' - Sc \frac{\gamma}{2} (\eta S' + 2 S') - C_r Sc S = 0 \quad (11)$$

The associated converted boundary conditions are

$$f(0) = V_0, \quad f'(0) = 1 + \lambda f'', \quad \theta(0) = 1 + \xi \theta', \quad S(0) = 1 + \beta S' \quad (12)$$

$$f'(\infty) \rightarrow 1, \quad \theta(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \quad S(\infty) \rightarrow 0 \quad (13)$$

The associated non-dimensional parameters are defined as

$$Pr = \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}, \quad \gamma = \frac{c}{a}, \quad \lambda = L \left(\frac{a}{2\nu} \right), \quad M = \frac{\sigma B_0^2}{\rho a}, \quad \xi = k_1 \left(\frac{a}{2\nu} \right),$$

$$\beta = k_2 \left(\frac{a}{2\nu} \right), \quad Sc = \frac{\nu}{D_B}, \quad C_r = \frac{C_1}{a}, \quad R = \frac{16T_\infty^3 \sigma^*}{3k^* k_f},$$

$$A_1 = \frac{1}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}}, \quad A_2 = (1 - \phi_2) \left[(1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \left(\frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f} \right) + \phi_2 \left(\frac{\rho_{s2}}{\rho_f} \right) \right],$$

$$A_3 = (1 - \phi_2) \left[(1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \left(\frac{(\rho c_p)_{s1}}{(\rho c_p)_f} \right) + \phi_2 \left(\frac{(\rho c_p)_{s2}}{(\rho c_p)_f} \right) \right], \quad A_4 = \frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f},$$

The density ρ_{hnf} , thermal conductivity k_{hnf} , dynamic viscosity μ_{hnf} , and heat capacitance $(\rho c_p)_{hnf}$ of the hybrid nanoliquid are specified by:

$$\mu_{hnf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}}, \quad \rho_{hnf} = (1 - \phi_2) [(1 - \phi_1) \rho_f + \phi_1 \rho_{s1}] + \phi_2 \rho_{s2},$$

$$(\rho c_p)_{hnf} = (1 - \phi_2) [(1 - \phi_1) (\rho c_p)_f + \phi_1 (\rho c_p)_{s1}] + \phi_2 (\rho c_p)_{s2},$$

$$k_{hnf} = k_{nf} * \left(\frac{k_{s2} + 2k_{nf} - 2\phi_2(k_{nf} - k_{s2})}{k_{s2} + 2k_{nf} + 2\phi_2(k_{nf} - k_{s2})} \right), \quad \text{where } k_{nf} = k_f * \left(\frac{k_{s1} + 2k_f - 2\phi_1(k_f - k_{s1})}{k_{s1} + 2k_f + 2\phi_1(k_f - k_{s1})} \right)$$

The another object of this problem is to calculate skin – friction coefficient (C_f), Nusselt number (Nu_x) and Sherwood number (Sh_x) and are given as

$$C_{fx} = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho U_w^2}, \quad Nu_x = \frac{x q_w}{k_f (T_w - T_\infty)}, \quad Sh_x = \frac{x q_m}{D_B (C_w - C_\infty)} \quad (14)$$

Where,

$$\tau_w = \mu_{hnf} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, \quad q_w = -k_{hnf} \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0}, \quad q_m = -D_B \left. \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0}, \quad (15)$$

Using the similarity variables the above equations take the form

$$\text{Re}^{1/2} C_{fx} = \frac{1}{(1-\phi_1)^{2.5}(1-\phi_2)^{2.5}} f''(0),$$

$$\text{Re}^{-1/2} \text{Nu}_x = -(1+R)A_4 \theta'(0), \quad \text{Re}^{1/2} \text{Sh}_x = -S'(0) \quad (16)$$

Where, $\left(\text{Re} = \frac{xU_w}{\nu_f} \right)$ represents the local Reynolds number.

3. Numerical solution of the problem

The variational Finite element process [43 – 46] is implemented to evaluate numerically above equations (9) - (11) with boundary conditions (12) - (13). Finite element method is one of the best method to solve both ordinary and partial differential equations numerically.

4. Results and Discussion.

This analysis examines the influence of slip effects on the heat transport coefficient in the flow of TiO₂/Al₂O₃-water hybrid nanoliquid over a stretching sheet. Variations in concentration, temperature, and velocity profiles are calculated and presented in graphs from Figures 2 to 20. Table 1 shows the thermophysical properties of the nanoparticles and water, while Table 2 compares the current numerical code with existing values.

Figures 2 to 7 illustrate the effect of volume fractions ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 on the concentration, temperature, and velocity profiles in both steady and unsteady cases of the TiO₂/Al₂O₃-water hybrid nanoliquid. The velocity profiles decrease with increasing ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , with a slightly higher reduction observed in the unsteady case. Conversely, both concentration and temperature

profiles increase with higher ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , due to the improved thermal conductivity of the nanofluid. This enhancement is also marginally higher in the unsteady case.

Figure 8 shows that velocity profiles decrease in both steady and unsteady cases with increasing values of the magnetic parameter (M), with a more pronounced effect in the unsteady case. This is attributed to the Lorentz force acting as a retarding force, which reduces the momentum boundary layer thickness. Figures 9 and 10 depict the temperature and concentration profiles, which increase with higher M values, with a greater amplification in the unsteady case. Figure 11 illustrates the impact of the Prandtl number (Pr) on temperature profiles, which decrease with higher Pr values, particularly in the steady case. Figure 12 shows that the concentration of TiO_2/Al_2O_3 -water hybrid nanofluid decreases with increasing Schmidt number (Sc) values, more so in the steady case. Figures 13 to 15 display the variations in the thickness of hydrodynamic, thermal, and solutal boundary layers with different suction parameter (V_0) values, indicating that the hydrodynamic boundary layer thickness increases while thermal and solutal boundary layers decrease with higher V_0 values, with a slightly greater effect in the steady case.

Figures 16 to 18 analyze the effect of the velocity slip parameter (λ) on concentration, temperature, and velocity profiles, revealing an increase in velocity and a decrease in temperature and concentration with higher λ values in both steady and unsteady cases, with a more pronounced effect in the steady case. Figure 19 shows that the thermal boundary layer thickness decreases with increasing temperature slip parameter (ξ) values in both cases, with a more significant effect in the steady case. Figure 20 demonstrates that the concentration profiles decrease with higher concentration slip parameter (β) values, with a more substantial reduction in the steady case.

Tables 3 and 4 present the effect of various parameters on the non-dimensional rates of mass transport, heat transfer, and velocity in both steady and unsteady cases. It is observed that the skin-friction coefficient, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number decrease with increasing ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , and M values. The non-dimensional rates of velocity, temperature, and concentration improve with higher V_0 values in both cases. As Pr increases, the dimensionless skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number increase, while the Sherwood number decreases. With higher λ values, the non-dimensional rate of velocity decreases, while the rates of heat and mass transfer increase. An increase in ξ values leads to a decrease in non-dimensional rates of velocity and heat transfer, but an increase in mass transfer rates. Finally, higher β values result in a reduction in the skin-friction coefficient and Sherwood number, while the Nusselt number increases.

5. Conclusion:

The present study has addressed TiO_2/Al_2O_3 – Water based hybrid nanoliquid heat and mass transfer analysis over a stretching sheet. The impact of velocity slip, temperature slip, chemical reaction and thermal radiation on TiO_2/Al_2O_3 – Waterbased hybrid nanoliquid flow is also analyzed. We have investigated the sway of different crucial parameters through plots and tables. The most noteworthy findings are as follows:

- (i) The volume fractional parameters of both nanoliquids ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 intensifies the thermal boundary layer thickness in both unsteady and steady cases of TiO_2/Al_2O_3 – Waterbased hybrid nanoliquid.
- (ii) Suction parameter (V_0) deteriorates the temperature and concentration of TiO_2/Al_2O_3 – Water based hybrid nanoliquid in both unsteady and steady cases.
- (iii) Both temperature and concentration sketches worsen with rising values of velocity slip parameter (λ) in both unsteady and steady cases of TiO_2/Al_2O_3 – Waterbased hybrid nanoliquid.

(iv) Rising values of (M) leads depreciation in the values of Sherwood number, Nusselt number and skin – friction coefficient.

(v) The dimensionless rates of heat transfer shrinks with rising values of (ξ) in both unsteady and steady cases of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ – Waterbased hybrid nanoliquid.

Data Statement: Data is available on request from the authors.

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Fig. 2. The Effect of (ϕ_1) on f' .

Fig. 3. The Effect of (ϕ_1) on θ .

Fig. 4. The Effect of (ϕ_1) on S .

Fig. 5. The Effect of (ϕ_2) on f' .

Fig. 6. The Effect of (ϕ_2) on θ .

Fig. 7. The Effect of (ϕ_2) on S .

Fig. 8. The Effect of (M) on f' .

Fig. 9. The Effect of (M) on θ .

Fig. 10. The Effect of (M) on S .

Fig. 11. The Effect of (Pr) on θ .

Fig. 12. The Effect of (Sc) on θ .

Fig. 13. The Effect of (V_0) on f' .

Fig. 14. The Effect of (V_0) on θ .

Fig. 15. The Effect of (V_0) on S .

Fig. 16. The Effect of (λ) on f' .

Fig. 17. The Effect of (λ) on θ .

Fig. 18. The Effect of (λ) on S .

Fig. 19. The Effect of (ξ) on θ .

Fig. 20. The Effect of (β) on S .

Nomenclature			
C_f	Skin-friction coefficient	ϕ_2	Nanoparticle volume fraction of Silver
k_f	Thermal conductivity of basefluid	Nu_x	Nusselt number
ϕ_1	Nanoparticle volume fraction of MWCNT Re_x		Local Reynolds number
C_∞	Ambient fluid concentration	u_∞	Velocity of mainstream
T_w	Wall constant temperature	T_∞	Ambient temperature
T	Fluid temperature	C	Fluid concentration
q_w	Wall heat flux	J_w	Wall mass flux
f	Dimensionless stream function	u_w	Velocity of the wall
K^*	Mean absorption coefficient	σ^*	Stephan-Boltzmann constan
Sh_x	Sherwood number	Pr	Prandtl number
(u, v)	Velocity components in x- and y-axis	R	Radiation parameter
τ_w	Shear stress	Sc	Schmidt number
M	Magnetic field parameter	D_m	Diffusion coefficient
Sc	Schmidth number	U	Composite velocity
(x, y)	Direction along and perpendicular to the wedge	C_r	Chemical reaction parameter
V_0	Suction parameter	C_w	Concentration at the wall
$s1$	First solid component	$s2$	Second solid component
t	time		
<i>Greek symbols</i>			
α	Thermal diffusivity of base fluid	ν	Kinematic viscosity
μ	Fluid viscosity	ρ_p	Nanoparticle mass density
S	Dimensionless nanoparticle volume fraction	η	Similarity variable
θ	Dimensionless temperature	λ	Velocity slip parameter
σ	Electrical conductivity	ξ	Thermal slip parameter
<i>Subscripts</i>			
∞	Condition far away from cone surface	hnf	hybrid nanofluid
f	Base fluid	nf	Nanofluid
<i>Superscripts</i>			

Table 1. Thermo - physical properties of water and nanoparticles [5].

Fluid	$\rho \left(\frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right)$	$C_p \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kgK}} \right)$	$k \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{mK}} \right)$	$\sigma(\text{Um})^{-1}$
Pure water	997.1	4179	0.613	0.05
Alumina (Al_2O_3)	3970	765	40	1×10^{10}
Titanium Oxide (TiO_2)	4250	686.2	8.9538	0.85×10^{10}

Table 2. Comparison of $(-\theta'(0))$ with the results of Waini et al. [42] for various values of (Pr) and $\phi_1 = 0, \phi_2 = 0$.

Parameter	Waini et al. [42]	Present Results
Pr	$(-\theta'(0))$	$(-\theta'(0))$
2.0	0.911353	0.911341
6.13	1.759682	1.759676
7.0	1.895400	1.895397
20.0	3.353902	3.353915

Table 3: Values of Skin - friction coefficient ($f''(0)$), Nusselt number $(-\theta'(0))$ and Sherwood number $(-S'(0))$.

Parameters			$f''(0)$		$-\theta'(0)$		$-S'(0)$	
ϕ_1	ϕ_2	M	Steady	Unsteady	Steady	Unsteady	Steady	Unsteady
0.01	0.01	0.3	0.27561	0.22693	1.55807	1.48628	0.58218	0.55978
0.05	0.01	0.3	0.23995	0.19811	1.40025	1.33083	0.57687	0.55492
0.10	0.01	0.3	0.19387	0.16100	1.22304	1.15858	0.56956	0.54827
0.01	0.01	0.3	0.25845	0.22785	1.58457	1.48965	0.57425	0.56458
0.01	0.03	0.3	0.22154	0.19754	1.45214	1.32024	0.55654	0.54875
0.01	0.05	0.3	0.18452	0.15265	1.21548	1.18547	0.52145	0.53245
0.01	0.01	0.5	0.10205	0.08450	1.17245	1.10912	0.55268	0.53237
0.01	0.01	0.7	0.05672	0.04704	1.14131	1.07876	0.54254	0.52289
0.01	0.01	1.0	0.02574	0.02143	1.11427	1.05220	0.53620	0.51148

Table 4: Values of Skin – friction coefficient ($f''(0)$), Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$) and Sherwood number ($-S'(0)$).

Parameters					$f''(0)$		$-\theta'(0)$		$-S'(0)$	
V_0	Pr	λ	ξ	β	Steady	Unsteady	Steady	Unsteady	Steady	Unsteady
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.19387	0.16100	1.22304	1.15858	0.36956	0.54827
0.7	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.23945	0.20186	1.47044	1.41611	0.64901	0.63017
1.0	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.31369	0.26986	1.81053	1.70699	0.75897	0.74398
0.5	8.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.19874	0.16107	1.44249	1.37299	0.56956	0.54827
0.5	10.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.19879	0.16203	1.64238	1.57122	0.56745	0.54758
0.5	12.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.20154	0.18754	1.82535	1.75457	0.55879	0.53214
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.53564	0.45830	1.35745	1.29418	0.61627	0.59410
0.5	6.2	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.46668	0.39980	1.37121	1.30725	0.62092	0.59847
0.5	6.2	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.38983	0.33453	1.38357	1.32099	0.62579	0.60307
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.19387	0.16100	1.22034	1.15858	0.56956	0.54827
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.19374	0.15968	1.07327	1.02331	0.56958	0.54958
0.5	6.2	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.19254	0.15745	0.95618	0.91632	0.57548	0.55235
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.19387	0.16100	1.22304	1.15858	0.44331	0.43031
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.19375	0.15986	1.22324	1.15875	0.36288	0.35412
0.5	6.2	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.19254	0.15847	1.22425	1.59872	0.30715	0.30085